

A REVIEW PAPER ON THE STUDY OF ROAD USER CHARACTERISTICS USING VISWALK FOR KR MARKET

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ABSTRACT

The rapid urbanization of cities such as Bangalore has led to a significant rise in both pedestrian and vehicular traffic, particularly in densely populated areas like KR Market. Understanding the dynamics of road user behaviour in these high-activity zones is essential for improving infrastructure and ensuring safety. This review paper explores the movement patterns of pedestrians, drawing on various studies to provide a comprehensive analysis. A key focus is on Viswalk, a sophisticated microscopic simulation tool for pedestrian dynamics, which facilitates the examination of critical behaviors such as walking speeds and crowd interactions. The insights gained from this analysis offer valuable information that urban planners and policymakers can leverage to make informed, data-driven decisions aimed at enhancing the safety and experience of road users in urban marketplaces.

Keywords: Road User Characteristics, Viswalk, KR Market, Bangalore, Traffic Simulation, Urban Pedestrian Behaviour

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1. INTRODUCTION

As Bangalore continues to grow, the city faces a range of challenges related to the management of pedestrian. KR Market stands out as one of the busiest commercial areas in the city, where significant foot traffic regularly intersects with vehicular movement. This high level of activity creates a complex environment that necessitates a deep understanding of how pedestrians. By examining these interactions, stakeholders can develop more effective traffic management strategies, enhance safety, and improve urban planning initiatives that address the unique needs of such crowded spaces.

This review paper explores various studies focused on the behaviors of pedestrians, shedding light on their movement patterns and interactions within high-density areas. A particular emphasis is placed on the use of simulation tools, such as Viswalk, which provide valuable insights into modelling these intricate dynamics. By utilizing Viswalk, researchers can analyse pedestrian flow, crossing behaviors, and the impact of crowding on safety. The findings from this comprehensive analysis aim to inform urban planners and policymakers, equipping them with the necessary data to make strategic decisions regarding infrastructure enhancements that cater to the challenges posed by densely populated urban environments.

2. CRITICAL REVIEW ON STUDY OF ROAD USER CHARACTERISTICS

Given are some of the most important reviews of the literature on road user characteristics that have been published on national and international magazines.

1. *“Pedestrian behaviour in urban area”*

This study investigates the intricate dynamics of pedestrian behavior within urban settings, focusing on how various elements such as environmental design, urban infrastructure, and socio-cultural factors shape the movement patterns and choices of pedestrians. The authors employ a combination of observational methods and quantitative analyses to capture the complexity of interactions between pedestrians and their surroundings. Their findings reveal that factors like sidewalk width, street layout, and the presence of visual cues significantly influence pedestrian flow and safety. The implications of this research are crucial for urban planners and policymakers, as it underscores the need for pedestrian-friendly designs that accommodate diverse user behaviors and enhance overall urban mobility.

2. *“Human factors of pedestrian walking and crossing behaviour”*

This paper examines the human factors that significantly influence pedestrian behaviors during walking and crossing situations. Through a detailed analysis of psychological, social, and environmental variables, the authors explore how these factors affect decision-making processes and safety outcomes for pedestrians. They highlight the importance of understanding individual and group behaviors, emphasizing that factors such as age, distraction levels, and environmental context play crucial roles in pedestrian safety. The study's insights provide valuable guidelines for designing safer pedestrian environments, advocating for strategies that consider human behavior in the planning and implementation of urban infrastructure.

3. *“A critical assessment of pedestrian behaviour models”*

The authors critically evaluate various models that attempt to describe pedestrian behavior, scrutinizing their effectiveness and applicability in real-world situations. This comprehensive assessment identifies strengths and weaknesses in existing models, such as their predictive accuracy and ability to account for complex human interactions.

By conducting a comparative analysis of different modeling approaches, the study highlights the necessity for improved methodologies that integrate real-time data and advanced simulation techniques. The insights garnered from this research are aimed at enhancing future pedestrian modeling efforts, ultimately contributing to more effective urban planning and safety interventions.

4. “Microscopic Traffic Flow Simulator VISSIM”

This paper provides an extensive overview of the VISSIM traffic flow simulation tool, which allows for the microscopic modeling of both vehicular and pedestrian traffic. The authors discuss the software's capabilities in simulating intricate traffic scenarios, including pedestrian interactions at various types of intersections and facilities. They present case studies that demonstrate how VISSIM can be used to analyze traffic patterns, evaluate different traffic management strategies, and assess the impacts of proposed infrastructure changes. The findings emphasize VISSIM's role as an essential tool for urban planners seeking to optimize traffic flow and improve safety for all road users.

5. “Modelling Movements in Shared-Use Paths with PTV Viswalk”

This research explores the use of PTV Viswalk to model pedestrian movements in shared-use pathways, focusing on how design features influence pedestrian behavior. The authors conduct simulations to evaluate various scenarios, assessing factors such as pathway width, user density, and conflict points between pedestrians and cyclists. Their results provide valuable insights into the dynamics of shared spaces, suggesting design modifications that could enhance user safety and comfort. By presenting practical recommendations for urban planners and transportation engineers, this study aims to improve the functionality and safety of shared-use paths in urban areas.

6. “The Application of Microscopic Models in the Study of Pedestrian Traffic”

This article discusses the application of microscopic modeling techniques to better understand pedestrian traffic flows and behaviors. The authors emphasize the advantages of these models in capturing detailed interactions among pedestrians, as well as between pedestrians and vehicles. Through a series of case studies, the research highlights how microscopic models can inform traffic management decisions and contribute to safer urban environments. The authors advocate for broader adoption of these modeling approaches in urban planning, emphasizing their potential to enhance the safety and efficiency of pedestrian infrastructure.

7. “Development of a Pedestrian Capacity Using a Movement Simulation Model in Malioboro, Yogyakarta, Indonesia”

This study focuses on the development of a movement simulation model to assess pedestrian capacity in Malioboro, a popular urban area in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. The authors utilize advanced simulation techniques to analyze pedestrian flow patterns, identifying critical points of congestion and potential safety hazards. By evaluating the capacity of existing infrastructure, the research provides recommendations for improving pedestrian facilities, thus enhancing the overall experience for users. The findings underscore the importance of using simulation models in urban planning to ensure that pedestrian spaces are both functional and safe.

8. “Simulation of Pedestrian Movement Over Different Facilities in Gangtok Using VISWALK Software”

Utilizing VISWALK software, this research simulates pedestrian movements across various urban facilities in Gangtok, India. The authors analyze how different design elements, such as facility layout and accessibility, influence pedestrian flow and behavior. By comparing various scenarios, the study identifies key factors that contribute to efficient pedestrian movement, providing actionable insights for urban designers and policymakers. The results highlight the significance of thoughtful facility design in promoting safe and effective pedestrian environments, reinforcing the need for data-driven approaches in urban planning.

9. “Microscopic Modeling of Pedestrian Movement in Urban Areas: A Case Study Using PTV Viswalk”

This case study employs PTV Viswalk to model pedestrian movement in a densely populated urban area, illustrating the software's capability to provide detailed insights into pedestrian dynamics. The authors discuss the methodology used to collect data and simulate pedestrian interactions, emphasizing the importance of realistic modeling in understanding how pedestrians navigate complex environments. The findings demonstrate that accurate pedestrian modeling is essential for informing urban infrastructure improvements and enhancing safety measures for pedestrians in urban settings.

10. “Modelling the Assessment of Intersections with Traffic Lights and the Significance Level of the Number of Pedestrians in Microsimulation Models Based on the PTV Vissim Tool”

This research investigates how pedestrian volumes affect traffic light-controlled intersections through the application of microsimulation models using PTV Vissim. The authors analyze various scenarios to understand the interplay between pedestrian behavior and traffic signals, providing insights into how pedestrian presence influences traffic flow. The study's findings highlight the need for traffic management strategies that account for pedestrian dynamics, aiming to improve safety and efficiency at intersections.

11. “Traffic Management of Pedestrian at Railway Stations using Vissim”

This paper explores the complexities of pedestrian traffic management at railway stations through the application of Vissim simulation software. The authors analyze the flow of pedestrians in these high-density environments, identifying potential bottlenecks and safety issues. By evaluating different management strategies, the study provides recommendations aimed at optimizing pedestrian circulation and ensuring the safety of all users. The insights from this research are critical for enhancing the design and operation of railway stations.

12. “Pedestrian-vehicle conflict analysis at signalized intersections using micro-simulation”

Through micro-simulation techniques, this study analyzes conflicts between pedestrians and vehicles at signalized intersections. The authors focus on identifying the key factors contributing to these conflicts, such as traffic signal timing and pedestrian behavior. The research findings offer practical recommendations for improving intersection design and management, aiming to reduce conflicts and enhance safety for both pedestrians and drivers.

13. “Modelling and Simulation of Pedestrian Behaviours”

This paper examines various modeling and simulation techniques used to capture pedestrian behaviors in different environments. The authors emphasize the importance of accurate simulations in understanding pedestrian interactions and the effects of environmental variables on behavior. The study contributes to the development of more effective urban design strategies that prioritize pedestrian safety and comfort, advocating for the incorporation of behavioral insights into planning processes.

14. “Safety Evaluation of Pedestrian Behavior and Violations at Signalized Pedestrian Crossings”

This research evaluates pedestrian behavior at signalized crossings, focusing on compliance with traffic signals and the factors leading to violations. By conducting observational studies, the authors identify common patterns of non-compliance and their implications for pedestrian safety. The findings highlight the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance safety at crossings, including educational campaigns and infrastructure improvements.

15. “Patterns of pedestrian attitudes, perceptions and behavior in Europe”

This study explores the diverse attitudes and perceptions of pedestrians across several European countries. The authors investigate how cultural, social, and environmental factors influence pedestrian behavior and perceptions of safety. By analyzing survey data and observational studies, the research provides valuable insights into the varying needs of pedestrians, informing public safety campaigns and urban design strategies that cater to diverse populations.

16. “Behavioral Issues in Pedestrian Speed Choice and Street Crossing Behavior: A Review”

This comprehensive review analyzes the various factors that influence pedestrian speed choices and crossing behaviors. The authors synthesize existing literature to identify key trends and insights, emphasizing the importance of understanding these behaviors for improving pedestrian safety. The study advocates for future research that focuses on the psychological and environmental factors that affect how pedestrians navigate urban spaces.

17. “Age and Group-driven Pedestrian Behaviour: from Observations to Simulations”

This research investigates the influence of age and social dynamics on pedestrian behavior, transitioning from observational data to simulation-based analyses. The authors emphasize how different age groups exhibit distinct crossing behaviors and preferences, suggesting that infrastructure design should accommodate these variations to enhance safety and accessibility for all users.

18. “Introducing Human Factors in Pedestrian Crossing Behavior Models”

This paper presents a novel approach to incorporating human factors into models of pedestrian crossing behavior. By analyzing psychological and environmental influences, the authors argue for the necessity of integrating these elements into simulation models to improve their accuracy and relevance. The findings aim to inform urban planners and traffic engineers about the importance of designing pedestrian environments that reflect human behavior.

19. “Modelling Pedestrian Behaviour Under Emergency Conditions: State-of-the-Art and Future Directions”

This study reviews current methodologies for modeling pedestrian behavior during emergencies, identifying existing gaps in research. The authors discuss the challenges faced in simulating these behaviors and propose future directions for research that could improve the understanding of pedestrian dynamics in crisis situations. The findings emphasize the need for adaptable.

20. “A Cognitive Human Behaviour Model for Pedestrian Behaviour Simulation”

This research introduces a cognitive model designed to simulate pedestrian behavior by integrating psychological factors and decision-making processes. The authors explore how cognitive aspects, such as risk perception and social influences, can be incorporated into simulations to produce more realistic pedestrian interactions. The study demonstrates that using a cognitive approach enhances the understanding of pedestrian dynamics, providing urban planners with valuable insights for creating safer and more efficient urban environments.

21. “Risky Pedestrian Behaviour and Its Relationship with Road Infrastructure and Age Group: An Observational Analysis”

This observational study investigates the relationship between risky pedestrian behaviors, road infrastructure characteristics, and the age of pedestrians. The authors analyze data collected from various urban locations to identify patterns in risky behaviors, such as jaywalking or ignoring traffic signals, and how these behaviors correlate with the quality of nearby infrastructure. The research emphasizes the need for tailored safety interventions that address the specific needs of different age groups, advocating for infrastructure improvements to enhance pedestrian safety across diverse demographics.

22. “Level of Service of Pedestrian Facilities: Modelling Human Comfort Perception in the Evaluation of Pedestrian Behaviour Patterns”

This paper evaluates the concept of level of service for pedestrian facilities by modeling human comfort perceptions and their impact on pedestrian behavior. The authors develop a framework to assess how different facility designs influence comfort and satisfaction among pedestrians. By conducting simulations and gathering user feedback, the study provides insights into the design elements that enhance pedestrian experiences, ultimately advocating for urban planning practices that prioritize human comfort and safety.

23. “Evaluation of Human Behaviour at Pedestrian Crossings”

This study conducts a thorough evaluation of human behavior at pedestrian crossings, focusing on factors that influence how individuals interact with traffic signals and vehicles. The authors utilize observational techniques and data collection to analyze pedestrian choices, waiting times, and compliance with traffic regulations. By examining these behaviors, the research aims to identify patterns and potential safety issues at crossings, providing insights that could inform the design of safer pedestrian facilities and improve traffic management strategies.

24. “Exploring the relationships between pedestrian behaviours and traffic safety attitudes in six countries”

This study investigates how pedestrian behaviors correlate with traffic safety attitudes across six different countries. The authors utilize surveys and observational data to identify common themes and variations in pedestrian behavior influenced by cultural and societal factors. By comparing these elements, the research sheds light on the complex dynamics between individual behaviors and broader traffic safety perceptions, offering valuable insights for enhancing pedestrian safety measures globally.

25. “A Framework for Enhancing the Spatial Urban Form of Informal Economies in India: The Case of Krishna Rajendra Market, Bangalore”

This research proposes a framework aimed at improving the spatial organization of informal economies within urban environments, specifically focusing on the Krishna Rajendra Market in Bangalore. The authors analyze the existing urban layout and identify challenges faced by informal vendors and pedestrians. By applying urban design principles and stakeholder engagement, the study aims to enhance the market’s functionality while ensuring pedestrian safety and accessibility.

26. “Verification and Validation of Viswalk for Building Evacuation Modelling”

This paper presents a comprehensive evaluation of the Viswalk simulation software's effectiveness in modeling building evacuation scenarios. The authors detail the verification and validation processes used to ensure the accuracy of the simulations in predicting pedestrian movement during evacuations. The findings highlight the importance of reliable simulation tools in emergency planning and response, providing insights into how Viswalk can be effectively utilized in real-world evacuation situations.

27. “Microscopic Simulation of Pedestrian Traffic in a Station Environment: A Study of Actual and Desired Walking Speeds”

This study employs microscopic simulation techniques to analyze pedestrian traffic within a station environment, focusing on the discrepancies between actual and desired walking speeds. The authors collect data on pedestrian movement patterns and preferences, allowing them to develop insights into how to optimize flow and reduce congestion in busy transit areas. The research underscores the significance of understanding pedestrian dynamics to enhance the overall experience in transportation hubs.

28. “Viswalk Microsimulation-Based Evacuation Modeling Of A Critical Infrastructure: A Social Force Model Approach”

This research applies the Viswalk microsimulation software to model evacuation scenarios for critical infrastructure using a social force model approach. The authors explore how pedestrian behaviors during emergencies can be effectively simulated to assess evacuation efficiency and safety. By integrating behavioral patterns into the model, the study provides a nuanced understanding of how individuals interact during evacuations, aiding in the design of more effective emergency response strategies.

29. “PTV Viswalk: Realistic Simulation of Pedestrian Flows”

This paper introduces PTV Viswalk as a tool for realistically simulating pedestrian flows in various environments. The authors discuss the features and capabilities of the software, emphasizing its applications in urban planning, safety assessments, and crowd management. By presenting case studies that demonstrate Viswalk's effectiveness, the research highlights the importance of accurate pedestrian flow simulations for informed decision-making in urban development and management.

3. “IDENTIFYING A SUITABLE PEDESTRIAN SIMULATION SOFTWARE—A CASE STUDY ON EMERGENCY EVACUATION OF CLASSROOM”

This study identifies the most suitable pedestrian simulation software for modeling emergency evacuations, specifically focusing on classroom scenarios. The authors evaluate several software options based on their ability to accurately represent pedestrian behaviors and movement dynamics during evacuations. Through comparative analysis, the research provides recommendations for educators and facility managers to enhance evacuation preparedness and safety in educational settings.

3.1. “Macroscopic Pedestrian Flow Modelling Using Simulation Technique”

This research explores macroscopic modeling techniques for pedestrian flow, employing simulations to analyze and predict crowd dynamics in various urban settings. The authors present methodologies for assessing flow patterns and densities, contributing to a better understanding of how large groups of pedestrians interact in public spaces. The findings aim to inform urban design and crowd management strategies, enhancing the overall safety and efficiency of pedestrian environments.

3.2. “Calibration and Validation of Pedestrian Simulation Parameters: A Case Study of Classroom Evacuation”

This paper focuses on the calibration and validation of simulation parameters for pedestrian movements, using a classroom evacuation scenario as a case study. The authors detail the methodologies employed to ensure that simulation outputs align with observed behaviors during evacuations. The research emphasizes the significance of accurate calibration in producing reliable simulation results that can effectively inform safety planning and emergency preparedness.

3.3. “Three-Step Performance Assessment of a Pedestrian Crossing Time Prediction Model”

This study presents a three-step assessment method for evaluating a pedestrian crossing time prediction model. The authors analyze various factors influencing crossing times, such as traffic conditions and pedestrian characteristics, to enhance the accuracy of predictions. By establishing a systematic evaluation framework, the research aims to improve traffic management strategies and enhance pedestrian safety at intersections.

3.4. “Pedestrian Simulation: A Review”

This review paper synthesizes existing literature on pedestrian simulation, examining various methodologies and technologies used in the field. The authors discuss the evolution of pedestrian simulation models, their applications in urban planning, and the challenges faced in accurately representing pedestrian behaviors. By identifying key trends and future research directions, the study provides a comprehensive overview of the state of pedestrian simulation research and its implications for urban development.

3. MAJOR FINDING FROM LITERATURE REVIEW

- **Influence of Human Factors:** The behaviors of pedestrians are notably impacted by various human factors, such as their perceptions of traffic safety and their adherence to traffic signals, which can differ significantly across cultures (2, 15).
- **Utilization of Simulation Tools:** Advanced simulation platforms like PTV Viswalk and VISSIM are instrumental in analyzing pedestrian movement patterns and behaviors, facilitating the exploration of various scenarios, including emergency responses and traffic management approaches (4, 9).
- **Modeling Emergency Evacuations:** Insights into pedestrian behavior during emergency situations can enhance the effectiveness and safety of evacuation plans, contributing to improved readiness for critical incidents (30, 28).
- **Importance of Calibration:** The reliability of pedestrian simulation models is contingent upon the careful calibration and validation of parameters, which ensures that these models accurately depict real-world pedestrian interactions and behaviors (32, 26).
- **Comprehensive Urban Management:** An integrated approach that melds infrastructure design, behavioral research, and sophisticated simulations is vital for developing safer and more effective urban spaces for pedestrians (25, 19).
- **Tailored Safety Interventions:** Interventions aimed at enhancing pedestrian safety can be more effective when based on cultural attitudes and observed behavioral patterns, improving compliance with traffic rules (18, 24).
- **Significance of Infrastructure Design:** The configuration of pedestrian facilities, such as crosswalks and transit stations, plays a significant role in shaping pedestrian behavior and overall safety outcomes (11, 22).
- **Data-Driven Decision Making:** The collection of empirical data through observations and simulations offers vital insights that can assist urban planners and traffic safety authorities in making informed decisions (23, 20).
- **Comparative Behavioral Studies:** Studies that compare pedestrian behavior across different countries highlight recurring themes, suggesting the potential for implementing shared strategies to enhance pedestrian safety internationally (17, 1).

4. CONCLUSION

- **Human Factors Influence:** Human perceptions of safety and cultural backgrounds greatly affect how pedestrians behave in cities.
- **Importance of Infrastructure Design:** Well-designed pedestrian facilities are essential for promoting safety and efficient movement in urban areas.
- **Role of Simulation Tools:** Simulation tools like PTV Viswalk and VISSIM are crucial for effectively modeling pedestrian movements and traffic situations.
- **Necessity of Calibration:** It is vital to calibrate and validate simulation models to accurately represent real-world pedestrian behaviors.
- **Tailored Safety Interventions:** Safety measures should be customized to suit the specific behaviors and attitudes of different pedestrian groups.
- **Empirical Data Insights:** Observational and simulation data offer important insights that can guide improvements in pedestrian safety.
- **Cross-Cultural Behavior Patterns:** Studies across various cultures reveal that pedestrian behaviors often share common characteristics, suggesting the need for universal safety strategies.
- **Call for Ongoing Research:** Continued research is essential to understand the changing patterns of pedestrian behavior due to urban development and environmental shifts.

REFERENCES

- [1] Parthiban, P., Anju, M.J., Asok, G., and Neeraja, P.G. 2021. Traffic Management of Pedestrian at Railway Stations using Vissim. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, NCIIE - 2021 Conference Proceedings.
- [2] Wu, J., Radwan, E., and Abou-Senna, H. 2016. Pedestrian-vehicle conflict analysis at signalized intersections using micro-simulation. *Transportation Research Record*, 2586, pp.90-100.
- [3] Ziemska-Osuch, M., and Osuch, D. 2022. Modeling the Assessment of Intersections with Traffic Lights and the Significance Level of the Number of Pedestrians in Microsimulation Models Based on the PTV Vissim Tool. *Department of Transport and Logistic, Gdynia Maritime University*, 81-225 Gdynia, Poland.
- [4] Fellendorf, M. and Vortisch, P., 2010. Microscopic traffic flow simulator VISSIM. *International Series in Operations Research & Management Science (ISOR)*, 145, pp.63-93.
- [5] Lopez-Rodriguez, M., 2022. Modelling movements in shared-use paths with PTV Viswalk. *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, 11(2), pp.123-140.
- [6] Oskarbski, J. and Gumińska, L., 2018. The application of microscopic models in the study of pedestrian traffic. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 231, 12th International Road Safety Conference GAMBIT 2018 - "Road Innovations for Safety - The National and Regional Perspective".2.
- [7] Wu, J., Radwan, E., and Abou-Senna, H. 2016. Pedestrian-vehicle conflict analysis at signalized intersections using micro-simulation. *Transportation Research Record*, 2586, pp.90-100.
- [7] Kumar, V., Banerjee, A. and Maurya, A.K., 2020. Simulation of pedestrian movement over different facilities in Gangtok using VISWALK software. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering (LNCE)*, 69, pp.517-528.
- [8] Muttaqin, M.Z., et al., 2023. Development of a pedestrian capacity using a movement simulation model in Malioboro, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. *International Journal of Transportation Engineering*.
- [9] Lopez-Rodriguez, M., et al. (2021). Microscopic modeling of pedestrian movement in urban areas: A case study using PTV Viswalk. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*.
- [10] Papadimitriou, E., Yannis, G. & Golias, J. (2009) 'A critical assessment of pedestrian behaviour models', *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 12(3), pp. 185-196. doi:10.1016/j.trf.2009.01.005.

- [11] Murrau, R. & Pinna, F. (2014) 'Pedestrian behaviour in urban area', *Journal Name*, pp. 1-12.
- [12] Koh, W.L., Lin, L. & Zhou, S. (2008) 'Modelling and Simulation of Pedestrian Behaviours', *Proceedings of the 22nd International Workshop on Principles of Advanced and Distributed Simulation (PADS)*, pp. 43-50.
- [13] Koh, W.L., Lin, L., and Zhou, S. 2008. Modelling and Simulation of Pedestrian Behaviors. *Proceedings of the 22nd International Workshop on Principles of Advanced and Distributed Simulation (PADS)*, pp.33-40
- [14] Koh, P.P., Wong, Y.D., and Chandrasekar, P. 2014. Safety Evaluation of Pedestrian Behavior and Violations at Signalized Pedestrian Crossings. *Safety Science*, 70, pp.143-152.
- [15] Papadimitriou, E., Theofilatos, A., and Yannis, G. 2013. Patterns of pedestrian attitudes, perceptions and behavior in Europe. *Safety Science*, 53, pp.114-122.
- [16] Ishaque, M.M., and Noland, R.B. 2008. Behavioral Issues in Pedestrian Speed Choice and Street Crossing Behavior: A Review. *Transport Reviews*, 28(1), pp.61-85.
- [17] Gorrini, A., Vizzari, G., and Bandini, S. 2016. Age and Group-driven Pedestrian Behaviour: from Observations to Simulations. *Collective Dynamics*, 1, pp.1-18.
- [18] Papadimitriou, E., Lassarre, S., and Yannis, G. 2016. Introducing Human Factors in Pedestrian Crossing Behavior Models. *Transport Research Procedia*, 15, pp.390-402.
- [19] Shiwakoti, N., Sarvi, M., and Rose, G. 2008. Modelling Pedestrian Behaviour Under Emergency Conditions: State-of-the-Art and Future Directions. *Proceedings of the 31st Australasian Transport Research Forum*, Melbourne, Australia: Department of Transport.
- [20] Hollmann, C. 2015. A Cognitive Human Behaviour Model for Pedestrian Behaviour Simulation. *PhD Thesis*. University of Greenwich, Faculty of Engineering and Science.
- [21] Escobar, D.A., Cardona, S., and Hernández-Pulgarín, G. 2021. Risky Pedestrian Behaviour and Its Relationship with Road Infrastructure and Age Group: An Observational Analysis. *Safety Science*, 143, 105420.
- [22] Cepolina, E.M., Menichini, F. & Gonzalez Rojas, P. (2018) 'Level of service of pedestrian facilities: Modelling human comfort perception in the evaluation of pedestrian behaviour patterns', *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 58, pp. 530-545.
- [23] Makó, E. (2015) 'Evaluation of human behaviour at pedestrian crossings', in *Proceedings of the 2015 6th IEEE International Conference on Cognitive Infocommunications (CogInfoCom)*. IEEE
- [24] McIlroy, R.C., Vũ Hoài, N., Bunyasi, B.W., Jikyong, U., Kokwaro, G.O., Wu, J., Hoque, M.S., Plant, K.L., Preston, J.M. & Stanton, N.A. (2020) 'Exploring the relationships between pedestrian behaviours and traffic safety attitudes in six countries', *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 71, pp. 146-157.
- [25] Patel, S., Furlan, R. & Grosvald, M. (2021) 'A framework for enhancing the spatial urban form of informal economies in India: The case of Krishna Rajendra Market, Bangalore', *SAGE Open*, 11(2)
- [26] Blomstrand Martén, J. & Henningsson, J. (2015) 'Verification and validation of Viswalk for building evacuation modelling', *Lund University, Division of Fire Safety Engineering*.
- [27] Lagervall, M. & Samuelsson, S. (2014) 'Microscopic simulation of pedestrian traffic in a station environment: A study of actual and desired walking speeds', *Independent Thesis*, Linköping University, Department of Science and Technology, Communications and Transport Systems.
- [28] Fariha, Z., Hoque, I., Quadir, S.T. & Meherin, M. (2023) 'Viswalk microsimulation-based evacuation modeling of a critical infrastructure: A social force model approach', *MDPI*
- [29] Beuti, T. (n.d.) 'PTV Viswalk: Realistic simulation of pedestrian flows', *PTV Group, Karlsruhe*.
- [30] Jain, H., Vanumu, L.D. & Rao, K.R. (2020) 'Identifying a suitable pedestrian simulation software—A case study on emergency evacuation of classroom', in *Recent Advances in Traffic Engineering*.

- [31] Das, P., Parida, M. & Katiyar, V.K. (2018) 'Macroscopic pedestrian flow modelling using simulation technique', *International Journal for Traffic and Transport Engineering*, 8(3)
- [32] Gaddam, H.K., Arya, A., Vanumu, L.D. & Rao, K.R. (n.d.) 'Calibration and validation of pedestrian simulation parameters: A case study of classroom evacuation', in *Proceedings of the Transportation Research Board (TRB) Committee ABR30 Standing Committee on Emergency Evacuations*.
- [33] Gruden, C., Ištoka Otković, I. & Šraml, M. (n.d.) 'Three-step performance assessment of a pedestrian crossing time prediction model', *Transactions on Transport Sciences*.
- [34] Rasouli, A. (n.d.) 'Pedestrian simulation: A review', *Journal of Transportation Engineering*.

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